

***INNOVATIVE APPROACH TO TEACHING ENGLISH IN SECONDARY
SCHOOLS.***

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Abstract: In this article, innovative approaches to English language teaching in secondary schools are discussed about the modern methods promoted by teachers for students' free thinking, speech depth, responsiveness, passion for language learning, and active participation in classes. is conducted.

Key words: general education, grammatical, lexical, phonetic, different ideas.

INTRODUCTION

Today, the interest of the young generation in learning foreign languages, especially English, is increasing. For this reason, in order to teach this language in general schools, pedagogues are required to make extensive use of innovative methods. The introduction of continuous teaching of foreign languages in the first grades of general education schools from 2013-2014 is a clear proof of this. English is almost a world language is shown as the most desirable language in all fields, therefore, not only in elementary grades, but also in the upper class, fully aware that learning the languages of economically, scientifically, and culturally developed times is the main factor in acquiring the achievements of world science and development. The importance of the language is definitely being paid attention to in choosing a profession among students. Language learning, like any other field, depends on the age of the students as well as the minds of the students.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Young children have a very high desire to learn a language, especially with today's information and communication tools. On the part of our country, the conditions created in schools, the fact that the classrooms are equipped with modern technologies, the provision of young educated personnel, the organization of television online classes on

online TV channels for all classes for independent study in addition to school classes, are commendable. Students of the 1st and 2nd grades may not understand the grammatical, lexical, phonetic, units of the language, but they can master the language at an excellent level through cartoons, games, and pictures. Accordingly, two methods are used effectively in grammar

- Inductive
- Deductive

In the inductive method, grammar rules are first explained to students and then reinforced through examples. This method is often useful for high school students. For example, tenses, prepositions, articles are known terms for high school students. In the deductive method, the topic is first introduced through certain games and exercises, and then it is explained based on the rule. Since elementary school students do not have knowledge about possessives, participles, verbs and other units, it is more effective to explain the topic to them through games and songs. For example, Can is a modal verb in English and is taught through handout materials.

- Can you play football
- Can you phone call
- It is very easy
- Can you do it Nansy?

According to psychologists, compared to older people, children are 70-80% more interested in new things, reading and learning. Children try to perform tasks that they cannot perform even in our daily life despite warnings. They get bored very quickly with the sameness, therefore, it is required from the teaching staff to organize lessons in new ways, in an unconventional way, to fully create the environment of the foreign language being studied.

Therefore, teachers should organize lessons using interactive, innovative and interesting methods. It is required to introduce working with students individually, in groups and in pairs, in the form of various competitions, in the form of games, with the use of colorful visual aids, and to prepare separately for each lesson. This type of lessons increases love and passion for the language, activates inactive students, and creates healthy competition among students. Competition is the foundation of growth.

DISCUSSION

Another important aspect in teaching English is to monitor the student's ability to fully absorb information. Children in the same group have different ideas, thoughts, worldviews and information reception. Accordingly, the teacher should conduct the educational process based on the characteristics of the character of each student. For example, in some students, the ability to remember by sight, and in another, to remember by hearing, may be formed by nature. According to these characteristics, English language learning is divided into 3 main directions: S Visual learning - remembering information by seeing S Auditory learning - remembering information by hearing S Kinaesthetic learning - learning through actions remembering information, taking into account the above characteristics, the teacher will create results and motivate the student to learn the language if the topic is explained or organized through games, during the lesson, during exercises, preparing role plays, games.

RESULT

Below we will consider some of the didactic games and pedagogical technologies that we can use in the lessons to organize such a meaningful lesson.

❖ Who is faster - the goal of the game is to develop the writing technique. The course of the game: the listeners are given cards with sentences written on them, and the words of the sentences on the cards are arranged in order. The student who writes first and in the correct order will be the winner. This game is more effective in higher grades.

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❖ Who am I? - the goal of the game is to develop speaking techniques. The course of the game: a student in the group comes out and describes something or a person without saying the name, and the rest of the students have to find who or what is according to the description. This game improves verbal literacy. This game is more for elementary school.

❖ The purpose of the continuous story-game is to develop vocabulary. The course of the game: the class is divided into 2 groups, and 2 types of stories are given in a semi-finished state, and the groups continue the story based on their fantasy and bring it to the end. Whichever group uses more new words is the winner. This game teaches students to work in harmony with each other. This game works better in higher grades.

❖ Noisy dictation-the goal of the game is to develop grammar. The course of the game: Students in the class are placed facing each other and must be able to correctly write the words of the student in front of them while listening to each other at the same time. This game will be a bit noisy and it is this noise that will allow them to develop word recognition even in this situation. Listening- improves listening skills. In English, words are not written as they are heard, for example in the word speak, the diphthong {ea} gives the sound [i] [spi:k]. If the student can understand the words correctly, then this is a good result. This game is used in elementary and high school.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it is worth noting that, taking into account the age and psychological characteristics of students, English is taught in different classes in general schools, and pedagogical innovative technologies help to fully satisfy their interest and needs in learning a foreign language. Based on modern lesson developments, the lessons are highly effective for students to learn the language.

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